

BALANCING DETAIL AND ASSEMBLY COMBINATIONS

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Abstract: This article covers the balancing of detail and assembly connections in simple language.

Keywords: Dynamic, static, aggregate, flywheel, prism, detail, engine.

Modern production does not satisfy the demand for the supply of spare parts for agricultural machinery. The best way to solve this problem is to repair the damaged parts. Currently, 30-40% of internal combustion engines of cars and tractors, 60-70% of agricultural machines can be repaired in various ways. Along with the improvement of simple methods of repair of details, the use of new effective technological methods is very effective. In this article, we will focus on modern methods of balancing detail and eating units.

Most of the unbalanced parts and assembly joints produce a large centrifugal force, which creates an additional large load on the supports of this element. In addition, an unbalanced load during rotation additionally vibrates the assembly unit, aggregate or the whole machine, as a result of which the wear and erosion of the parts increases, the fixed parts become loose, the reliability and long service life of the machine decreases. Therefore, many parts are checked for balance before assembly, that is, they are balanced. The displacement of the center of gravity of the rotating masses relative to the axis of rotation of the detail and assembly unit means that they are not balanced. This is caused by the non-uniformity of the density of the detail material, the violation of bulletproofness during processing, uneven eating, lack of accurate assembly, etc. Balancing is divided into static and dynamic balancing.

The detail is statically balanced on special stands and devices with horizontal prisms or rotating rollers. Detail - the flywheel 2 (Fig. 1) is fastened to the special tool 1, and the stent (device) prism 3 is attached to Fig. 1, a) or rollers 4 to Fig. 1, b). If, when rotating, it returns to the same bottom position at any angle, it is considered unbalanced. In order to balance the part, it is necessary to weld the same load on its opposite side, to cover it with liquid, to pour washers, or to bend and drill a part of the metal from the heavier (lower) side of the part. The part is statically well balanced if it always stops in different positions when rotated through any angle. Static balance is more accurate in rotating rollers than in prisms.

Figure 1. The scheme of static balancing of details.

Dynamic balancing. The essence of dynamic balancing is as follows. If a long piece of unbalanced mass m (Fig. 25) is statically balanced with a load Q , then two centrifugal forces F are formed around its axis when it rotates. These forces, which are equal in magnitude and act in opposite directions at a distance l from each other (on the shoulder), create a torque Fl . As a result, an additional load falls on the shaft supports, which vibrates this unit and the whole machine. The load and vibration on the bearings increases with the increase in the rotation frequency of the part. In order

to balance the resulting double force F_l moment, it is necessary to give the detail a force equal to it, but in the opposite direction to the double force F_{l1} moment.

Figure 2. Detailed dynamic balancing scheme

Thus, dynamic balancing consists in balancing the resulting pair force moment with the help of balancing loads or by removing the masses that create this moment. Dynamic balancing is performed on special balancing machines. The part is mounted on special supports of the machine, and when these supports rotate, the part vibrates under the influence of unbalanced forces. The vibration amplitude of the supports indicates the value of inertial centrifugal forces and their moments. If the part is dynamically balanced, the supports will stop vibrating. As in detailed static balancing, it is balanced by removing a part of the metal, by drilling or placing plates, washers, welding and hoes.

Usually, short parts larger than their diametrical length (flywheels, pulleys, discs, blades, etc.) are statically balanced, while long parts (crankshafts and cardan shafts and crankshafts) whose length is much larger than their diameter are dynamically balanced.

To sum up, today agriculture is being enriched with agricultural machines of various districts. Today, various agricultural equipment for tillage, sowing, fertilizing, spraying, harvesting, and harvesting equipment from Germany, the USA,

Russia, China, and other countries are used and supplied with spare parts when necessary. there is a need to provide. Of course, it is very expensive to bring these spare parts from abroad in foreign currency. That is why it is more economical to prepare and repair some details of the equipment and machinery available in the technical service centers located in the regions and districts.

References.

1. Fundamentals of machine accuracy Q.X T “Economy and finance” 2015-180 p.
2. Basics of machine repair and trust. Yoldashev Sh.U. Publishing House of Uzbekistan, 2003-422p
3. Кучаров, А. С. ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ НЕФТЬ-ГАЗ САНОАТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ СТРАТЕГИЯСИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ.
4. Кучаров, А. С. (2019). ОЦЕНКА ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ ТУРИЗМА ТАШКЕНТСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. In Студенческие научные исследования в сфере туризма и спортивного менеджмента (pp. 110-112).
5. Odinayev, A., Qalandarov, R., & Xolmatov, B. (2023). PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGY OF REPAIRING BLOCKS AND CYLINDER LINERS. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL THEORY AND COMPUTER SCIENCES, 4(1), 97-99.
6. Кучаров, А. С. (2020). Роль таможенных органов в совершенствовании внешнеторговых операций Республики Узбекистан. Наука, образование и культура, (8 (52)), 15-19.
7. Rozimurod, Q., Kocharovich, O. A., & Ogli, Y. S. F. (2023). ABOUT VIBRATION NOISE PROBLEMS IN MACHINERY AND MACHINES USED IN COTTON GINNING FACTORIES (CCP). Science and innovation, 2(A4), 220-226.

8. Кучаров, С. А., & Шағдаров, Н. (2021). ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ФАНИНИ ЎҚИТИШДА АХБОРОТ ВА ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (1-Махсус сон), 119-122.

9. Кучаров, С. А. (2021). TECHNOLOGIYA TA'LIMI O 'QITUVCHISINING TECHNOLOGIK MADANIYATI. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (1-Махсус сон), 116-118.

10. Кучаров, А. С., Бобожонов, А. Б., & Хошимов, Д. З. (2021). ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ СОҶАСИДАГИ ИСЛОҲОТЛАР ДОИРАСИДА АХБОРОТ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР АСОСИДА МАЛАКАЛИ ПЕДАГОГ КАДРЛАР ТАЙЁРЛАШ. Перспективы развития высшего образования, (9), 75-88.

11. Choriev, R., & Kucharov, S. (2023). METHODOLOGY OF USING ELECTRONIC TEXTBOOKS IN THE FIELD OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION. Science and innovation, 2(B1), 371-373.

12. Кучаров, С., & Одинаев, А. (2021). Технологик таълимнинг касб танлашдаги аҳамияти. Общество и инновации, 2(4/S), 369-373.

13. Кучаров, С. А. (2021). АХБОРОТ-ТА'ЛИМ МУНИТИДА КАСБИЙ О'ҚИТУВЧИЛАРНИ ПЕДАГОГИК FAOLIYATGA TAYYORLASH: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.53885/edinres.2021.86.21.061> Kucharov Sardorbek Akmalovich Termiz davlat universiteti, «Technologik ta'lim» kafedrası o'qituvchisi. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (1-Махсус сон), 116-118.

14. Ko'charov, S. (2022). PREPARATION OF PROFESSIONAL TEACHERS FOR PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES. Физико-технологического образование, (3).

15. Kucharov, A. S., Bobojonov, A. B., Kamalova, E. A., Ishmanova, D. N., & Ishmukhamedov, B. J. (2022). Digitalization of the Strategic Management Systems of the Oil and Gas Industry Enterprises. In Big Data in the GovTech System (pp. 119-125). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

16. Kucharovich, O. A., Akmalovich, K. S., & Qorajonovich, Z. A. (2022). UMUMTA'LIM MAKTABLARINING TEXNOLOGIYA DARSLARIDA "YOG 'OCHGA ISHLOV BERISH STANOKLARI VA ULARNING TUZILISHI" MAVZUSINI O 'QITISH METODIKASI. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(3), 320-327.

17. Kucharov, A. S. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF "SMART AGRICULTURE" TECHNOLOGIES IN AGRICULTURE COMPLEX OF UZBEKISTAN. Архив научных исследований, 2(1).

18. Dusyarov, X. C., Odinayev, A. K., & Kucharov, S. A. (2021). CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING STUDENT KNOWLEDGE IN TECHNOLOGY CLASSES. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(3), 1168-1173.

19. Kucharov, A. S., Kamalova, E. A., & Nurmamad, D. (2021). 7 State Regulation of Competitive Relations. New Institutions for Socio-Economic Development: The Change of Paradigm from Rationality and Stability to Responsibility and Dynamism, 5, 63.

20. Akmalovich, K. S. (2022). TEXNOLOGIK TA'LIMNING KASB TANLASHDAGI AHAMIYATI. Лучший инноватор в области науки, 1(1), 357-360.

21. Kucharovich, O. A., & Akmalovich, K. S. (2022). AXBOROT KOMMUNIKATSIYA TEXNOLOGIYASI RIVOJLANISH IMKONIYATLAR METADALOGIYASIDA. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(9), 111-114.

22. Kucharovich, O. A., & Akmalovich, K. S. (2022). Innovative Teaching Methods and their Practical Application in Technological Education Classes. Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences, 1(5), 305-309.

23. Kucharov, A. S., & Shermukhamedov, A. T. (2017). Perfection of transport-logistical system of Uzbekistan. Journal "Austria Science N, 8, 2017.

24. Choriev, R. K., Khujakeldiev, K. N., Kucharov, S. A., Khayitova, S. D., Abdiev, N., & Amirqulov, X. Q. (2022). Pedagogical Problems Of Distance And Traditional Education. Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results, 2895-2904.

25. Azamov, A. A., Kuchkarov, A. S., & Holboyev, A. G. (2019). The pursuit-evasion game on the 1-skeleton graph of a regular polyhedron. ii. Automation and Remote Control, 80, 164-170.